

REFLECTION OF DIALECTICAL LAWS IN SECULAR PROCESSES

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Abstract. In the modern world, the principles of secular society dominate, on the one hand, and on the other, the process of the initial revival of religious consciousness, one of the ancient sources of popular culture. That is why religion has become a social institution on the agenda of many issues related to the role and status of modern society. Issues such as secularism, which implies the free, independent and independent activity of the spheres of public life. In this sense, this article is devoted to the analysis of this complex and controversial social process and its relevance.

Keywords: secularization process, religious mythology, rational approach, moderate secularism, acute secularism, theocracy, totalitarian system, pluralistic approach, metaphysics, tolerance.

Secularization, which is currently one of the most comprehensive topics in the social sciences, is one of a number of pressing problems related to the transformation of the place of religion in society since the middle of the last century and its significance. Over the past period, much research has been done on this issue, and an interpretation of secularization as a social phenomenon has been proposed. Nevertheless, "secularization" is still one of the concepts, the contents of which are not sufficiently disclosed.

The term "secularism" is defined in the Oxford Dictionary as follows: "Secularism is the theory, form of faith, ideology and political method that distinguish secularism from other phenomena (usually associated with religion, as well as sanctification and metaphysics)."[1, p. 379]. This definition is distinguished

by the fact that it is devoted to the formalization of secularization as one of the political mechanisms for managing a renewed society.

When we think about secularization, it becomes clear, first of all, that serious changes and updates occur in the place and role of religion as a social institution in society. In our opinion, secularization is a complex of political, economic and sociocultural reforms aimed at eliminating any ideological monopoly and setting the priorities of liberalism by modernizing the traditional social system.

The results of the study of this problem show that there are four generalizing principles of this theory:

At first. Dialectics of secularization and modernization. It is well known that modernization has led to the sustainable development of industrialization, urbanization, rationalism, educational opportunities and the influence of the media. According to some scholars, the modernization that has occurred in various aspects of society has been interpreted as a key factor in secularization. In particular, P. Berger emphasizes that there is a dialectical connection between modernization and secularization, which occurred in the middle of the XIX century. In his opinion, modernization does not always lead to secularization, but always leads to pluralism. The emergence of secularization was associated only with the modernization of the economy and its sectors, in which capitalism and industrialization played a major role. "If everyday life is mainly associated with work and related problems, then there will be a high degree of secularization. Religious symbols do not disappear due to their close connection with state institutions and the family "[2, p. 126], the scientist wrote.

The second. The principle of unity and struggle between the contradictions between science and religious doctrine. The concepts of "religiosity" and "secularization" have long been interpreted as contradictory principles, and this interpretation has been observed since the secular culture, which arose under the influence of the secularization process, began to prevail. These contradictions, manifested in the form of a struggle of religious convictions and

rational thinking, laid the foundation for the development of both as an independent field.

In the new and recent period, science, based on rational thinking, began to reject the ideas of absolute religious teaching. In particular, O. Comte puts forward his theory of positivism, emphasizing the replacement of the theological and metaphysical worldview with the "positive method" and the rejection of "absolute knowledge." Although his positivist philosophy caused some controversy, it served to oust theological and metaphysical approaches from the field of science.

The third. The influence of secularization on quantitative and qualitative changes in society. Secularization is accompanied by a decrease in the influence of religious institutions in the cultural and political life of society, as well as stagnation in individual religiosity. Secularization is an uneven and multi-vector process associated with changes in the religious situation, religious institutions and religious worldviews, which leads to a decrease in the importance of religions and religiosity in society. It is also not a universal process, meaning that not all realities associated with secularization are equally important.

The fourth. The general principle of secularization. Secularization is a unique feature of modern society, which is of particular importance. Indeed, at present, religious symbols and values traditionally do not fulfill the function of complete control over society. The role and importance of modern science and technology in solving existing problems is increasing. In this sense, secularization is an irreversible process. In this regard, D. Uzlaner states the following: "Today there is no clear evidence that Europe is returning to the religious situation in the Middle Ages" [3, p. 35]. However, the processes taking place in the religious sphere have shown that secularization does not develop on the basis of a single form and model. In particular, D. Martin predicted the process of secularization since 1960 in his "Threshold of the disappearance of the concept of secularization" [4, p. 250], "General theory of secularization" [5, p. 358] criticized in the works.

The essence of the concept of secularization is based on the characteristics of a theoretical interpretation and principles, and the following general conclusions are drawn.

The first, secularization is a general and abstract concept from a logical point of view, and from the point of view of content - one of the relative concepts because of the relationship between religiosity and secularism. The definitions of this concept are of the nature of time and space and, as a rule, mean the formation and development of the state and society on the basis of liberalism, free from the absolute guidelines of a particular religion.

The second, secularization is reflected in social life on the basis of several principles. As traditional societies are gradually updated in the process of modernization, this always requires the application of secular principles.

The third, despite the fact that religion and science have long been considered two opposing parties, now both parties act on the basis of partial compatibility (subcontract) through partial confirmation and partial denial of each other.

The fourth, secularization has undergone functional changes as a result of a decrease in the influence of religious institutions in the cultural and political life of society. This change was clearly reflected in the economic and political directions and activities of the countries of the world, and the purely theocratic form of government, which was not influenced by secularization, became history.

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